

Technical debt description groups

Defining Security Debt: A Case Study Based On Practice

Group #	Technical debt description (TDD)	# of respondents	Characteristics also mentioned for SD?
TDD1	Deliberate accumulation of TD	22	Yes
TDD2	Not deliberate accumulation of TD	15	Yes
TDD3	TD effect on maintainability	15	No
TDD4	TD accumulated due to technology change	10	Yes